

Visualizing Student Makerspace Portfolios

Racial Diversity and Assessment in Makerspaces

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ABSTRACT

Over the past two decades, the Makerspace movement has grown from a grassroots project to one that is widely considered mainstream. However, few studies have explored how these programs document student learning experiences and what they attended to show. This study aims to investigate the results of two consecutive surveys from 77 Makerspace sites to relay a complicated story about the people, programs, and practices involved in making. Information visualization (IV) refers to a collection of representation to present synthesized and visualized information. IV provides a promising way to present complex data and enable the audience to develop an overview quickly as well as examine specific information. By analyzing and transferring the survey data into visualizations, we address some of the challenges researchers face in dealing with survey data and how those challenges can be overcome. We also elaborated the details of our design from an iterative process of prototyping, testing, analyzing, and refining data visualizations. The immediate objective of this study was to develop a modular, interactive, and informative tool illustrating the unique characteristics and potential impact of the Makerspace movement. Results show that graphic manipulation techniques enable users to make sense of multidimensional data and provide the flexibility to communicate the results to a broader audience.

KEYWORDS

Information visualization, Makerspace movement, Open-portfolio

1 INTRODUCTION

The notion of “maker” implies a mindset of do-it-yourself through making and calls for self-driven learning in an open-ended exploration. “Makerspace” is an umbrella term, referring to communities of makers, who co-construct knowledge, develop communal goals and solve community problems. In the recent decade, the maker movement urges educators to rethink and reflect the existing educational pedagogy and methodology and provides a promising way to “reimagine education” from an innovative perspective [12].

The Makerspace movement has grown significantly since President Obama’s call to action to support the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) fields [8]. Since then, the number of libraries, schools, and nonprofits offering Makerspace

classes has expanded to become a nationwide phenomenon. However, the question remains as to the impact these classes have on students and how much is documented. By shifting the paradigm from passive, lecture-based learning to active, participatory learning [2], it allows different stakeholders to understand students’ learning while engaging in learning activities, interacting with tools and people and producing artifacts. However, little is known on how learning and making activities are documented in those programs.

Two groups that have been actively working to address these issues are Maker Ed and Creativity Labs. Maker Ed offers professional development for educators centered on establishing a “common framework for documenting, sharing and assessing learning through portfolios.” Creativity Labs is a research lab at Indiana University that is responsible for the research part of the project. Over the course of the past 4 years, both groups have collected data from their host sites regarding student and teacher demographics, subjects offered, classroom locations, and high-level outcomes. Their goal is to collect information about youth-serving Makerspaces, their assessment instruments and general practices along a variety of different metrics. In 2014 and 2017, both groups collaboratively interviewed managerial members from the current most active Makerspace sites and collected their thoughts and opinions on various issues, e.g. population and learning assessment.

In this study, we focus on investigating the results of surveys conducted by both groups and to help users explore the intersection of people, places, activities and assessments in the world of making. The final product will be likely an interactive dashboard with a collection of visualizations to allow users to get a quick overview of the development of Makerspaces and explore the detailed aspects by manipulating various variables built into specific visualizations as well as comparing and contrasting among all visualizations. The interactive dashboard will be supported by a web-based data analytical platform. In addition, users may then mouse over each site to see key site data. Included, also, will be high-level graphics for selected sites showing the number of students, their racial diversity, and subject matter coverage.

The client for this project is Anna Keune, a lead graduate researcher for the Maker Ed Open Portfolio Project investigating how openly documented portfolios of youth projects can serve to reframe assessment. The intended audiences for our visualization are the stakeholders in the project; educators, practitioners, and researchers in the maker movement, and interested members of the public.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Gee [5] emphasized the new media literacy in learning, which is to construct knowledge and meaning from various media, and argued for designing and incorporating good learning principles in digital media and learning. He elaborated three essential aspects to investigate the emerging principles for deep and practical learning. First, nurture and develop a participatory culture to enable learners to get access to professional work and encourage them to produce products by using digital tools. Second, take advantage of social networking tools to empower learners to engage in diverse and collaborative activities. Third, using new digital media to promote learner competency in language learning, complex thinking, problem-solving skills and other critical skills required as a 21st-century learner.

Peppler and Bender [12] introduced and explained the maker movement, the current development, and characteristics of Makerspaces and relevant projects [12]. Making is pervasive in every walk of life. Makerspaces have increasingly grown nationally and internationally in various contexts, from school-based programs to projects situated in libraries and museums connecting all types of disciplines and fields. Generally, maker movements prompt innovation in education in three ways, including 1) empower learners to contribute ideas to community good and match with local needs, 2) encourage different stakeholders to participate and mitigate cultural boundaries in participation and 3) build cross-disciplinary communication and increase mutual trust and growth.

Sheridan et al. [13] studied the function and effect of Makerspaces on learning by using a collection of analytical approaches to examine three Makerspaces and examined how learners learn by making in practices. Rooted in constructionist view, "making" emphasizes both interpersonal and intrapersonal relationships between learner with the artifacts. Learners need to constantly develop, adjust and interpret the artifact in which serves as "an evolving presentation of the learner's thinking" [13]. The process of designing and making viewed as interactive and dynamic along with the learner's process of developing knowledge. To scaffold and support an innovative learning, a well-designed learning environment is necessary and critical.

3 DESIGN RATIONALE

We aim to improve upon existing geographic maps by maximizing task-domain attributes such as name, category, context, value, and interface-domain features such as size, color, opacity, density to illustrate the complexities facing educators in this field.

The map visualization includes an additional data layer exploring socioeconomic climates as well as a temporal slider for a historical presentation. It is accompanied by simple-to-understand graphics and charts to highlight essential topics. An interactive dashboard not only provides a compact overview with selectable items for drilling down into further detail on demand, but it also allows the client to create new data stories.

According to Shneiderman [14], the fundamental guiding principle for advanced graphical design "might be summarized as the Visual Information-Seeking Mantra: overview first, zoom and filter, then details-on-demand" [14]. We have kept this in mind when selecting data types. In addition to historical geospatial information,

our goal for the final deliverable was to include some combination of the following data types: heat maps, diverging stacked bars, a circular hierarchy, bipartite networks and scatter plots Figure 1.

Figure 1: A draft plan for visualization.

3.1 Geographical Data

As the central focus of this visualization, a map provides an overview of the entire data set. It contains a movable field-of-view box and a zoom feature for more detail. Rather than creating a separate timeline, we wanted to use a slider above the map to highlight the chronological development of Makerspaces in relationship to their geography. An underlying data layer would then show a color-coded range of socioeconomic values for added context (a choropleth map).

3.2 Heat Map

Heatmap would be used to show variance in the data. These are most effective in small multiples, based on similar attributes and arranged in a row for easy comparison.

3.3 Back to Back Bar/Population

Bar charts of any type encode data by length and are easy to interpret. Population pyramids are horizontal bars sharing a spine to compare/contrast two populations or two sets of data side by side. We considered using a deviation bar graph instead, in which different bars are going in positive and negative directions since it could be valuable to show that a differential exists or change has occurred, not just the raw numbers.

3.4 Circular Hierchy

A layout of nodes on a circle with links crisscrossing the central area used to show relationships between Makerspace types, assessment types, and learning competencies that could not be conveniently demonstrated otherwise. This visualization type would provide an interesting counterpoint to statistical and geospatial data for a more holistic view of this project.

3.5 Bipartite Network

A layout of nodes in columns with links crisscrossing the central area is used to make a smooth comparison between two sets of items (i.e., Makerspace type versus school subject).

3.6 Scatter Plot

Exploring correlations through scatterplots can generate insights that may influence a strategy or course of action. This is the most common way to show the relationship between two continuous metrics, where data from both groups plotted as points.

4 RELATED WORK

In this section, we examine three relevant visualizations conducted by previous researchers and elaborate how their work informed our decision-making process for choosing appropriate format of visualizations. The list of selected visualizations includes a geographical framework to depict geographical information and identify relevant geographical location and two contrasting cases to a collection of numerical referenced visualizations.

A geographical framework was extremely important to this project. As such, most of the visualizations on the topic of Makerspaces are geospatial. From previous literature review in the current report of the Makerspace Open-Portfolio project, we found that the rich geographical information provided in the data hasn't been fully explored except the location and the role of each Makerspace. For example, in Figure 2, two issues emerged from our analysis. First, in some occasions, map legends tended to hinder readers' effective interpretation of the information without purposeful design. Second, user problems associated with 2-dimensional map data "are to find adjacent items, containment of one item by another, paths between items, and the basic tasks of counting, filtering, and details-on-demand" [14] were insufficiently addressed. In our project, we intended to resolve these issues by constructing concise and interpretable legends and utilizing a 3D and interactive map to allow readers to identify and compare multi-dimensional information.

When using a set of visualizations, problems might occur regarding the inconsistent visual elements, the excessive and inappropriate use of a specific type of visualization. In Figure 3, the simple styling seems to grab readers' attention from a glance. However, due to the inconsistent color encoding and overuse of donut charts, the graphs look noisy and fail to keep readers' attention on the most important information. As Tufte stated, "The only worse design than a pie chart is several of them, for then the viewer is asked to compare quantities located in spatial disarray both within and between pies" [18]. Visual encoding, therefore, was the primary consideration as our work is developed.

In contrast, Figure 3 presents an excellent example of getting the point across and enabling the user to understand what the authors

Figure 2: Two different representations of Canadian university Makerspaces by McCue [10]

are trying to convey quickly. In the figure, icons are used to inform the donut chart and colors used with care. Stoke, Steward, and Sleigh [15] reminded us that "creating the dataset is only half of the job. A bigger question remains: how can it be used to inform and benefit Makerspaces and the public more generally?" [15]" Although a long-form infographic is not suitable for this project, we examined these two cases help us to avoid the same design issues and promote our understanding of how to communicate our points efficiently.

Figure 3: Infographics showing the state of Makerspaces in the U.S. (left) and in the U.K. (right)

5 DATA ANALYSIS

The data received from Creativity Labs consisted of a collection of report briefs and two surveys: one from the Maker Space Group and another from the Open Portfolio Project. The Maker Space Group survey contained 54 responses from sites where the group did classes while the Open Portfolio Project contained 36 responses. Both surveys consisted of SPSS output but the questions asked and responses returned were not always the same.

5.1 Data Cleansing and Data Wrangling

A great deal of effort was devoted to cleaning, merging, and formatting the survey data. There were duplicate records, values that were out of range, geographic errors, reporting errors, missing values, closely matched fields that needed to be validated before merging, and coding differences between the string and numeric survey answers. Some dates were found on Makerspace websites or estimated in the absence of more detailed information. Despite the small sample size, we concluded that non-responses did not raise concerns and would not prevent us from conducting an effective analysis. Where possible, our group attempted to unify the two surveys as follows:

- Each field was examined and, where possible, fields from each survey that asked the same question and were answered with the same values were aligned to make one field. For example, each survey asked: "What state is your class in?" In these cases, we created one field ("State") and used that for the analysis.
- Questions that were similar, but not the same, were grouped. For example, each survey asked the respondent about what subjects were covered (engineering, physics, etc.). Of the

18 school subjects covered, 14 of them were common between the two surveys. The subjects that were not common were: dance, engineering, environmental science, and foreign language. It is possible that foreign language was considered a subset of language arts but we did not have enough data to support that conclusion.

- Fields were checked to make sure that they used the same scale. For example, the fiPortfolio Importance question used four options on the Maker Site survey but five options on the Open Portfolio one. In this scenario, we did not align the fields since the meaning of the responses would be slightly different between the two surveys.
- Finally, fields that had no corresponding question in the other survey were left aside in a Maker Site and Open Portfolio grouping. These are presented to the user, but we could not provide compare-and-contrast visualizations to the end user.

Once the data was put together, we began the process of analyzing what was there and what we could do with it. The data were plugged into Google Facets, and the values of fields were examined and, if needed, cleansed. One common issue we found was that respondents were misinterpreting "Country" for "County". Likewise, various permutations of "US", "USA", and "United States" were merged into a single value: "USA". Finally, the Racial Diversity questions, which were of high interest to our group, required some cleaning. Specifically, the Maker Site survey did not require the percentage of racial groups at a given site to add up to 100%. The reason may have been to account for students from biracial backgrounds (Open Portfolio had an option for "2+ Races"). In these scenarios, the percentage was flattened to 100% - assuming the proportion was correct but the total was not.

After the data analysis and cleanup process was complete; the revised survey data was sent out to the group to begin various analyses. Care was taken to make sure everyone was always using the same version to avoid conflicting results as some minor changes to correct the data had to be made later in the visualization development process. Overall, however, the data was of high quality and did not require significant revisions, other than unification, for it to be usable for our clients' needs. Combining the two files resulted in a final data set consisting of 85 entries with a total of 77 Makerspaces (8 sites were common to both surveys) across nine countries. An exploratory data analysis revealed five categorical variables: demographics, subject matter, setting and context, assessment, and facilitation (see Appendix A for a summary of data elements).

5.2 Data Analysis Algorithms

Transformations performed on the original data are as follows:

- (1) Data Cleansing in Google Facets
- (2) Combined Excel surveys using VLOOKUP
- (3) Corrected/normalized geographic locations
- (4) Flattened racial proportions that did not add up
- (5) Extrapolated year based on operation years id field on Maker Site Survey
 - Corrected or estimated dates for sites over 5 years old

- (6) Responses that were too inconsistent, such as reported number of participants/staff per year, disabilities and free meal estimates, were discarded
- (7) Extrapolated setting type based on Type of organization or institution field
- (8) Extrapolated program type based on Open Portfolio survey unique fields
- (9) Merged duplicate sites
- (10) Created new sheet with numeric values
 - Replaced Yes with 1 and No with 0
 - Converted string rankings to numeric scale where 0 = none/other/never and from 1 up to 6 = least to most; 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree
 - Replaced True with 1 and False with 0
 - Replaced Not Familiar with nulls
 - Replaced Other with something more specific
- (11) Created new sheet with (mostly) string values
 - Replaced 1 with string based on column name and 0 with null
 - Selected fields based on group discussions and usefulness in network visualizations
- (12) Removed all fields except the areas of interest

5.3 Statistical Report

5.3.1 Racial Diversity Analysis. One of the first analyses done with the unified dataset was to look at the racial diversity of both programs and to allow the end user to select geographical areas of interest. Each program asked about the racial distribution of the students, and we took that data and compared it to the racial distribution of the surrounding county. The goal was to see if the distribution was skewed within the program - if they were targeting minorities or traditionally disadvantaged students, was that being accomplished? To that end, we gathered the U.S. 2010 Census data for the county that the site was in and analyzed the student profile along two axes.

The first was to see how the composition of the class broke down when compared to the surrounding neighborhood. In the Figure 4 and Figure 5, the Actual column represents the proportion of students that belonged to each racial category while the Expected column represents the county breakdown - the proportion of races that we would have expected if we had randomly sampled the county.

Generally, the two surveys reported a similar result with Black students having an outsized representation compared to the population at large. For Maker Site, this came from the reduced representation of White and Asian students while Open Portfolio had fewer Hawaiian/Pacific Islander students than we would have expected.

To better represent this data, we came up with a second set of graphs Figure 6 and Figure 7 which shows the total delta between Actual and Expected. These graphs, we found, really highlighted the total difference and had a much better impact.

In terms of potential targeted, it seems that Makerspaces were likely to get a larger outsized group. One suggestion we had for Maker Site was to include Pacific Islanders and add an option for bi-racial students (to bring them in line with Open Portfolio). Also, after looking at the racial data, we realized that Maker Site had not

Figure 4: Proportion of racial diversity in Makerspace Sites Survey (2014)

Figure 5: Proportion of racial diversity in Makerspace Sites Survey (2017)

Figure 6: The difference of diversity above/below expected in Maker Site survey (2014)

included gender data which would have been useful as the focus on Maker Programs is encouraging diversity in the STEM/STEAM fields and this is one of the most common comparisons that are made in the literature.

Figure 7: The difference of diversity above/below expected in Open Portfolio survey (2017)

5.3.2 Gender Diversity Analysis. We conducted extensive gender analysis in DataCracker and found few relationships between gender and many other variables in the dataset. For example, when we compared school subject to student gender, males were shown to be less interested in "Drama" than males on average as shown in Table 1.

While the male staff was more likely to report that youth could create an argument from evidence, the data revealed that there was no difference in actual youth performance in this area. Females were slightly less represented overall yet their participation in STEM fields remained consistent with the net average. We looked for patterns across different variables, but this did not yield actionable insights. Since we were mainly interested in female participation in the STEM, we decided not to pursue this area of inquiry aggressively.

5.3.3 Standard Deviation Test for School Subjects. We conducted a standard deviation test for study categories. We found that three groups of subjects emerged based on the similar range of standard deviations within each group. The first group includes the subject of "Drama, Biology, and Chemistry", which share similar SD values around 0.35. The second group consists of subjects of "General Comp, General Science, Physics, Mathematics, Computer Science" that share the similar SD values around 0.50. Lastly, the third groups are the subjects of "Music" and "Language Arts and Digital" with SD values around 0.45. We also completed a person correlation test between the Black racial group and computer science and found a value of 0.271, which is higher than other racial groups in the data set.

We also ranked the popularity of class subjects (High to Low)

- Visual Arts
- Computer Science
- General Science
- Physics
- Mathematics
- Language Arts
- Social Studies
- Drama
- Chemistry

Table 1: Subject by Youth Gender in Open Portfolio survey (2017), 95% confidence level

Average	Male	Female
Biology	55.2	42.7
Chemistry	39.7	58.3
Computer Science	52.5	45.6
General Science	50.7	43.1
General Computer Class	53.9	44.4
Language Arts	53.9	42.7
Digital or Media Arts	55.7	40.7
Drama	32.5	46.8
Mathematics	47.1	46.9
Music	58.8	33.6
Other School Subjects	43.3	52.4
Physics	52.9	45
Social Studies	65.4	32.2
Visual Arts	49.4	43.1
Dance	NaN	NaN
Engineering	57.9	40.2
Environmental Science	57.6	42.0
Foreign Language	65	30
NET	53.1	42.8

5.3.4 T-Test Results. After applying the t-test for race population between white and other races, we put our alternative hypothesis as 20 for the mean difference. We have obtained the results below. We can interpret these results as showing that the white population mean is bigger than 20 for all racial groups with high P values as shown in Table 2, Table 3, and Table 4.

Table 2: A summary of t-Test on Paired Two Sample (Hispanic, White) for Means

	Hispanic	White
Mean	18.87	42.85
Variance	607.569	923.603
Observations	90	90
Pearson Correlation	-0.374	
Hypothesis Mean Difference	20	
df	89	
t Stat	-9.12	
P(T<=t) one tail	1.0596E-14	
t Critical one-tail	1.662	
P(T<=) two tail	2.1192E-14	
t Critical two tail	1.986	

Table 3: A summary of t-Test on Paired Two Sample (Asian, White) for Means

	<i>Asian</i>	<i>White</i>
Mean	11.174	42.855
Variance	253.983	923.603
Observations	90	90
Pearson Correlation	-0.1185	
Hypothesis Mean Difference	20	
df	89	
t Stat	-13.637	
P(T<=t) one tail	8.04737E-24	
t Critical one-tail	1.662	
P(T<=) two tail	1.60947E-23	
t Critical two tail	1.986	

Table 4: A summary of t-Test on Paired Two Sample (Black, White) for Means

	<i>Black</i>	<i>White</i>
Mean	17.736	42.855
Variance	390.025	923.603
Observations	90	90
Pearson Correlation	-0.2880	
Hypothesis Mean Difference	20	
df	89	
t Stat	-10.507	
P(T<=t) one tail	1.4404E-17	
t Critical one-tail	1.662	
P(T<=) two tail	2.8807E-17	
t Critical two tail	1.986	

6 DISCUSSIONS

Based on our analysis, we have two levels of findings to report, including the visualization findings and the statistical findings. As described above, we focus three dimensions of the study, which are student equality, subject matter coverage, and geographic distribution. To get an in-depth view, we continuously added and compared variables to each dimension to investigate the interrelationship and the interplay among variables.

6.1 Visualizations in Mock-Ups

The mock-ups have four different kinds of visualizations, which were published to an interactive dashboard.

- An interactive geographical map (see Figure 9) was used to illustrate the geographical difference regarding portfolio importance and to set to the per capita income of US. Also, the chronological development of Makerspaces could be traced by their geographical locations. This visualization quickly helped us to identify the development of Makerspaces.
- The chronological development was presented regarding heat maps (see Figure 10) with a range of indicators, including ethnicity, race, and gender, on two levels (student

level and staffing level). This visualization could help us to understand not only the basic demographic information but also to examine whether staffing attributes relate to students' demographic difference.

- A circular hierarchy graph (see Figure 11) depicted the interrelationship assessment related items with learning issues. This visualization could enlighten us to dig into the use of assessment and its possible impact on learning.
- Bipartite network (see Figure 12) on the interrelationship between subject and program type provides us a micro-lens into the focus of Makerspaces in the subject with the afforded environments. Below is a list of tools we used to wrangle data and populate visualizations.

6.1.1 Data Wrangling and Visualization Tools Used.

- Alteryx software with a drag-and-drop interface to prepare, blend and analyze data [1]
- DataCracker: web-based survey analysis software [3]
- Excel: traditional spreadsheet software [11]
- Google Facets: open source data visualization tool used to explore patterns and relationships between variables in large data sets [7]
- Gephi: open source network analysis and interactive visualization platform [6]
- LibreCalc: free and open source spreadsheet software [9]
- Tableau: drag-and-drop business intelligence tool [16]
- Trifacta: data wrangling and exploration software [17]
- yEd: free general-purpose diagramming program using automatic layout algorithms to arrange data visually [19]

6.1.2 Geographical Map. This map Figure 8 used the (mostly) string value file in step 11, imported into Alteryx and transformed using the algorithm below (see Appendix B). Data from the Excel was read, key fields were pivoted, and the null rows were filtered out. The results were merged into one file and output as a new spreadsheet that could be used in Tableau.

Figure 8: Geographical Map, Makerspaces by Setting and Portfolio Importance in Relation to Per Capita Income, 1973 to 2017

6.1.3 Heat Maps. The heat maps were created in Tableau using the same data set as the geographical map. Two variables were compared at once in a similar way to how scatter plots would be

Network Visualization
Generated from Bipartite network from assessments and Subjects
March 24, 2018 | 11:36 PM EDT

Figure 13: Bipartite Graph on Connecting, Assessments and Subjects, 1973 to 2017

the past decade. This should be considered as we develop our temporal representations.

- Although gender equity itself does not seem to be an issue, the data show some differences that could have been better explored with larger sample size.
- There are strong connections between certain topics, formats, assessments, and learning outcomes that deserve more attention.

There are so many dimensions that could be explored including the effects of staff education on attitudes and outcomes that it would be easy to generate an almost endless variety of visualizations. Thus, the final product must cut through the noise so that the user gains a deep understanding with little effort.

7 VALIDATION AND REDESIGN

During the intermediate project phase, our group surveyed six volunteers to solicit their feedback about our preliminary data visualizations and their thoughts on the tool going forward. The comments could be grouped into three categories:

- Lowering the density of the data display to avoid overwhelming and confusing the user.
- Improving the usefulness of some graphs and removing others that didn't tell a compelling story.
- Incorporating numerical values into our displays rather than visual encodings (colors and size).

The first problem mostly arose from the fact that the network graphs we constructed from the data were very densely packed. Sites tended to offer a wide variety of formats (events, meetups, open studio time) at each of the Makerspace types (drop-in, fablab, etc.). This made the encoding complex and challenging to understand and didn't tell a good story as it, necessarily, boiled down to "every space tends to offer every format." Changing the layout could have been helpful along with the adding weights and sizing to edges and nodes, respectively, for the audience to better understand the visualization. However, to reduce cognitive load,

we chose to remove some graphs that were irreducibly complex (topic co-occurrence and format-space type networks) and rely on more straightforward graphs that directly conveyed their story to the user. The final interactive tool will give the user access to the more extensive data set as they drill down into each element. However, it is still presented as tight, concise stories that are easy to interpret and understand.

In addition to the first issue, the comments we received suggested incorporating or removing features to improve the usefulness of some graphs. If a graph was not intuitive (as above), we opted to either remove it from our dashboard or to rework it into a more meaningful product. Our main takeaway was that while the graphs looked excellent, they were hard to interpret without being able to hover, click, or otherwise manipulate the data. In particular, the Makerspace sites tended to be grouped in dense clusters. When looking at a world map, it became difficult to distinguish how many sites there were, where they were, and what the differences were between them. An abundance of colors added to the confusion. For this reason, our final presentation features major geographic regions with clear markings, allowing the user to focus on areas that are of interest to them, which helps alleviate this issue.

Finally, some of our graphs were reworked to incorporate numerical values to supplement the visual encodings utilized. For example, our volunteers seemed to generally understand and like the heat maps showing how enrollment and staffing had changed over the years - we were trying to see if efforts to recruit more women and older children were working as shown in Figure 14. However, without a grounding of what scale we were using (percentage or nominal values) they were confused as to how comparable the numbers were - were we trying to show the balance between men and women? Alternatively, just that total enrollment was up? What was the range of values (high to low)? To resolve these issues, we added gradients showing the scale of the data, and a clear legend will help with interpretation. We referred to research on motif simplification which leveraged repeating variables to make the network visualization less complicated to the eyes of the audience [4]. The team was thankful for the feedback, and it helped us understand that having an independent person reviewing the visualization helps spot things that we may not be aware of ourselves since we intrinsically understand our visualization since we were the ones that developed it.

As we approached the conclusion of our project, our group took steps to improve the user experience and address the comments that were brought up during validation, such as adding explanatory text to improve how users interact with and make the best use of the tool. We did not find anything significantly wrong with our study and, instead, worked to improve the story being told. Our most significant priority was ensuring that our visualizations were easy to understand, especially for members of the public who might have difficulty accessing Makerspace sites yet are interested in the idea of "making" or who are looking for opportunities to involve themselves in "maker-like" activities. Thus, our work will give these users a high-level overview of Makerspace sites and an opportunity to explore relevant elements through a dashboard interface. This dashboard will be designed in Tableau and uploaded to Tableau Public, allowing users easy access to the visualization as a webpage. We will include views of where the sites are geographically located,

Figure 14: Revised heat map

an estimate of how well they are serving their community via racial profiles, and subject matter coverage (given the emphasis of Makersites on STEM/STEAM). We will also continue to review the data to see if there are additional insights we can glean from it.

8 CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

The limitations of this study included a small survey sample size, respondent errors or skipped questions, not enough matching fields across surveys, differences in measurement and rating scales for similar fields, inadequate explanations for calculated fields such as diversity indices, and occasionally, poor question structure (e.g., staff age). We used our best judgment about how to fix or exclude items during the data cleansing and preparation stage.

Clearly, the most significant challenge with survey results is a lack of precision. We respected this weakness by looking at the most prominent trends, not unusual differences in data. Our group analyzed variables using standard deviation instead of raw numbers or averages. We quickly discovered that it was all too easy to bombard users with complex graphs that would be impossible to digest. It was a continuing struggle to find the right balance between the quantity and quality of information presented. We also had to consider which data types would produce the most actionable, rather than just the most interesting, results for the client. Over past decades, the Makerspace movement has engaged different stakeholders to participate in a variety of learning activities and events, so our work must remain relevant to a broad audience. Our study seeks to present a common language for these stakeholders to communicate similar ideas and promote a mutual understanding.

For practitioners and Makerspace managers, who are part of Makerspace movement but eager to know how other Makerspaces develop and use portfolios, our study provides a means for them to develop in-depth perspective by comparing Makerspace sites. For researchers and the broader academic community, our study could be viewed as an opportunity to evaluate and reflect upon

the development and the focus of Makerspace sites for the purpose to inform future directions of Makerspace studies. However, the conclusions derived from this study require careful consideration of the assumptions and inferences, given the small number of participants.

Future endeavors should seek to unify survey structures and create as many common metrics as possible for more in-depth analysis since it is only with a substantial body of evidence that the more complicated and nuanced aspects of Makersite survey data can be addressed. We recommend that future researchers conduct micro-level studies in specific Makerspace sites to examine female student engagement in STEM-related activities, including how they document and reflect upon their participation and learning compared to their male counterparts. Because we found strong connections among specific topics, formats, assessments, and learning outcomes, we also recommend that future work explore teachers' facilitation and use of different tools to bring the second layer to the analysis and improve our understanding of these connections. We were excited to see that both projects have been successful at recruiting minority students and we would hope that the trend continues. Finally, as staff educational attainment appears to have an impact on assessment use and learning outcomes, investigating the inter-relationship between staffing and other learning-related variables is necessary.

9 CONCLUSION

In this paper we showcased the several visualization types that can give the best understanding of context of Makerspace portfolios in terms of racial diversity and their assessments. We begin with giving examples from several literatures about the Makerspace movements. Second, we gave how we approached our design idea for the visualizations that we are trying to showcase. Second, we began by giving examples of several visualization types and how they used in real-world context. We provide how we handle the data analysis which consist from several steps which are cleaning, statistical research, and visualization part.

Moreover, we provide the discussions for various types of visualizations to understand student equality, subject matter, and geographic distribution and we continuously added new variables to understand the relationships between the variables.

Furthermore, after the design step we get with six individual to get their feedback about the several visualizations that we created. Their feedback is being used to create our final visualization step which we provided in an interactive Tableau [16] dashboard as shown in Figure 15, bigger picture of the visualization is shown in the appendix section. We made visualization to be understandable to any user from any background. Our interactive visualization gives users ability to see and filter any information live.

Lastly, we provide the challenges that we faced during the data preparation as well as the data visualization steps. We also include some of the opportunities that we identify during these steps.

Figure 15: Interactive Dashboard Final Visualization from Tableau

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A APPENDIX

Table 5: A summary of data elements in Makerspace Open-Portfolio project

Broad Field	Level of Measure	Attribute Type
Site Name	Nominal	String
Location	Ordinal	Geolocation
Date Established	Ordinal	Date
Size of Population Served	Ordinal	Integer
Staff/student demographics	Ratio	Percentage
Makerspace Type	Nominal	String
Organization Type	Nominal	String
Setting Type	Nominal	String
Program Formats	Nominal	String
Program Topics	Nominal	String
School subjects	Nominal	String
Pedagogical Framework	Nominal	String
Learning Competencies	Ordinal	Scale
Assessment Type	Nominal	String
Assessment Importance	Ordinal	Scale
Staff Education	Ratio	Integer

Figure 16: A data flow diagram of the cleaned dataset undergoing division, transformation, and joining in Alteryx for use in Tableau

Figure 17: A screenshot of the workflow to generate heat maps in Tableau

Figure 18: A screenshot of imported and transformed parameters using yEd

Network Analysis Toolkit (NAT) was selected.
 Implementer(s): Timothy Kelley
 Integrator(s): Timothy Kelley
 Reference: Robert Sedgewick. Algorithms in Java, Third Edition, Part 5 - Graph Algorithms. Addison-Wesley, 2002. ISBN 0-201-31663-3. Section 19.8, pp.205
 Documentation: <http://wiki.cmlu.edu/display/CISHELL/Network-Analysis-Toolkit+%2BNAT%29>
 This graph claims to be directed.

Nodes: 60
 Isolated nodes: 7
 Node attributes present: label, xpos, ypos, zpos

Edges: 828
 No self loops were discovered.
 No parallel edges were discovered.

Edge attributes:
 Did not detect any nonnumeric attributes.
 Numeric attributes:
 min max mean
 weight 1 2 1.00966

This network seems to be valued.

Average total degree: 27.6
 Average in degree: 13.8
 Average out degree: 13.8
 This graph is not weakly connected.
 There are 8 weakly connected components. (7 isolates)
 The largest connected component consists of 53 nodes.
 This graph is not strongly connected.
 There are 8 strongly connected components.
 The largest strongly connected component consists of 53 nodes.

Density (disregarding weights): 0.2339
 Additional Densities by Numeric Attribute

Figure 19: A screenshot of file documents and data process in Sci2

- MERGE col: Biology, Chemistry, Computer_Science, General_Science, General_Computer_Class, Language_Arts, Digital_or_Media_Arts, Drama, Mathematics, Music, Other_School_Subjects, Physics, Social_Studies_History, Visual_Arts, Dance, Engineering, Environmental_Science,
- MERGE col: Community_events, Courses_or_classes_for_youth_workshops, Drop_in_programs_for_youth, Educator_meetups, Educator_training_or_professional_development, Member_programs, Open_studio_time_for_youth,
- MERGE col: kind_makerspace, kind_hackerspace, kind_drop_in, kind_youth_center, kind_fablab, kind_innovation_lab, kind_design_lab, kind_idea_lab, kind_science_lab, kind_STEM, kind_STEAM, kind_other with: '|' as: 'MakerspaceType'
- MERGE col: Pre_and_post_tests, Rubrics, Rubrics, Portfolio_assessment, Peer_assessment, Exit_surveys, Short_answer_questions, Self_assessment, Adult_modeling, Essay_items, Multiple_choice_items with: '|' as: 'assessments'

Figure 20: A screenshot of using Trifacta to identify makerspaces types, assessments, subjects and makerspace events.